

Deep-sea mining and Ocean Carbon Workshop

Summary Report

27th August 2024, 10.00 – 14.00 CET/09.00 – 13.00 GMT

Online Teams Meeting

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Stakeholder Sign-Up Sheet:	https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUsignup

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Executive Summary

The OceanICU project hosted an online stakeholder workshop on the 27th August 2024 focussed on understanding the interactions between deep-sea mining and ocean carbon. It was attended by 23 participants.

A survey on initial perceptions of the interactions of ocean carbon, climate change, and deep-sea mining was sent to participants prior to the meeting. At the workshop, a series of presentations introduced the OceanICU project, an overview of the pre-workshop survey results, and a 'primer' on ocean carbon. Time was provided for open discussion (Q&A), followed by an interactive session focused on co-developing a consensus conceptual model of ocean carbon and the deep-sea social-ecological system.

Key discussion topics included:

- **The importance of the ocean in relation climate change and carbon:** recognising the role of the ocean and its living organisms in sequestering and storing carbon.
- **Biodiversity and habitats:** the importance of considering biodiversity and habitats when considering carbon issues was emphasised.
- **The dimensions of the deep sea and the scale of deep-sea mining activity and its impacts:** The true scale of the deep ocean and the activities that take place there need to be fairly represented, as most current representations do not show this. This point was raised several times.
- **Deep-sea ecosystem services:** The role of the deep-sea in supplying multiple ecosystem services, including climate regulation, cultural heritage, genetic and medicinal services, and intrinsic value, in addition to role of deep-sea mining in providing metal security and the meeting demand for minerals need to be considered and balanced.
- **The relationship between on-land and at-sea activities:** this theme was multi-faceted, including discussions around the relative impacts of deep-sea mining on ocean ecosystems and the climate compared to other land-based activities or land-based mining. It was highlighted that deep-sea mining may not result in less on-land mining, and that demand for these minerals may change as technology progresses.
- **Policy uncertainties:** it is currently unclear if and how deep-sea mining will progress. Policy and legislative regulation was a consistent underlying theme across all discussions.
- **Multiple key knowledge and evidence gaps:** were highlighted as a key issue. For example, there is currently no consensus on whether the scale of impacts will be large and irreversible, or insignificant in relation to the scale of oceans and deep-sea habitats, carbon cycling and sequestration in general. The need for further evidence on the mechanisms and scales of impacts, and a lack of evidence on deep-sea habitats themselves was reiterated.

These discussions will inform the ongoing research trajectories in the OceanICU project. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the workshop participants and wider stakeholder group, with additional workshops planned in the future.

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1. Introduction

The ocean plays a vital role in slowing climate change absorbing approximately 25% of the carbon we add to the atmosphere. Deep-sea mining for minerals has the potential to support the green technology sector and help society move towards carbon neutral green growth. However, the relationship between deep-sea mining and ocean carbon is complicated; deep-sea mining also has the potential to affect carbon sequestration processes in the deep sea. Deep-sea sediments (>1000m depth) account for approximately 90% of total ocean sediments and approximately 84.5% of ocean carbon sediment stocks (Atwood et al., 2020). Where there is overlap with mining activity, these sediment carbon stocks may be affected. Currently, the relationship, interactions, scale of potential impacts and trade-offs between deep-sea mining, marine carbon, and climate change are not well known or understood.

1.1 The OceanICU Project

OceanICU is a Pan-European project funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI running from November 2022 to October 2027. It has a consortium of 31 partners across 15 countries. The overall project aim is to produce new data, information and understanding on the role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle. Demands for ocean resources such as food from fish, materials such as trace metals, and blue energy (wind, wave, tidal) are increasing. These increasing demands may affect the uptake of carbon by the ocean due to changes in emissions, industrial processes, and climate change itself. OceanICU recognises the need for knowledge and tools to support decisions makers, managers, and ocean users manage ocean resources, and understand how their interactions with the ocean may affect ocean carbon and hence climate change.

OceanICU is developing new tools that include parameters relevant to management and industry (Figure 2.1). As such, we aim to establish current understanding, perceptions, and needs of stakeholders in relation to oceanic carbon and identify key emerging threats and trajectories. This information will then be used to define scenarios of interest and societal relevance for use in a decision-support tool (DST), and to inform an oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, scenarios, and trade-offs, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services. As part of this, we will produce a multi-sectoral, multi-pressure oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services.

Figure 1.1 Overview of processes considered in the OceanICU project.

2. Workshop Goals and Set-Up

2.1 Goals

This workshop was the first engagement with deep-sea mining (DSM) and mineral extraction stakeholders as part of the OceanICU project. The goal of this workshop was to document stakeholder understanding of the links between deep-sea mining, mineral extraction and ocean carbon.

2.2 Intended Outcomes

During the workshop, the OceanICU project, goals and some background on ocean carbon were presented, in addition to some of the pre-workshop survey outcomes. We carried out an exercise to co-produce a mental model of the deep-sea mining-carbon system, including the elements that should be included in such a system, and the types of links between those elements. Through this, the intended outcomes were the identification of knowledge gaps and areas of interest or need, potential vulnerabilities, and opportunities for intervention. This will inform the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU, specifically feeding into developing future scenarios and management/policy questions that are relevant to stakeholder needs, attempting to fill knowledge gaps, and providing input to the development of decision support tools and outputs from the project. We intend to build on the outputs of this workshop with future stakeholder engagement events and workshops.

2.3 Meeting Set-Up

The meeting was hosted online via teams with collaborative note-taking via a Sharepoint word document

- Additional resources were provided to participants via Sharepoint and remained available for editing/contributing one-week post-meeting.
- The meeting was recorded for note-taking purposes. Chatham house rules (information disclosed during a meeting may be reported by those present, but the source of that information may not be explicitly or implicitly identified) were used to ensure open dialogue.

- Participants were encouraged to contribute with respect in whichever way felt comfortable (speaking up, posting in the Teams chat, or writing directly in the notes document).

2.4 Participant Profile

A total of 21 individuals participated in the survey and/or workshop. Sixteen attended the workshop (Figure 2.1), and 19 people completed the survey in advance of the workshop (with 14 doing both). The workshop was attended by representatives from NGOs, managers and responsible authorities, advisory bodies, deep-sea mining and associated industries, and academia (Figure 2.2). Participants from the deep-sea mining industry had the greatest representation at the workshop, forming 31% of the group, followed by those from NGOs (25%) and responsible authorities/management (25%).

Figure 2.1 Participant profile of attendees at the workshop¹. Mining industry includes deep-sea mining companies, polymetallic nodule collectors and equipment manufacturers. Participant profile of the survey responses varies slightly from this².

¹ One individual was associated with both Academic/Research and an NGO, but was assigned to academia here as their primary affiliation. One individual was associated with Management/Responsible Authority and Academic/Research and was assigned to Management/Responsible Authority here.

² Two individuals (1 from industry and 1 Management/Responsible Authority) did not complete the survey but did attend the workshop. Five people (1 from Industry, 1 NGO, 2 Management/Responsible Authority and 1 from Academic/Research) completed the survey but did not attend the workshop. Survey participant profile was: Industry: 5 individuals, 26%; Management/Responsible Authority: 5 individuals, 26%; NGO: 5 individuals, 26%; Academic/Research: 3 individuals, 18%; Consultancy: 1 individual, 5%.

Figure 2.2 Deep-sea mining and Ocean Carbon Workshop Attendees and Survey participants (for terms see glossary, Appendix 8.2)

2. Current understanding of interactions between deep-sea mining – and ocean carbon

Dr Richard Sanders and Dr Matthias Haeckel introduced the topic of ocean carbon and deep-sea mining and to provide context and a common baseline understanding.

Dr Sanders described our current understanding of where organic and inorganic carbon is stored in the ocean. The amount of carbon stored in all marine biomass is small (5Gt), compared to e.g. 2200Gt stored in marine sediments (ICES, 2024). Despite this relatively small amount of stored carbon, marine animals can sequester much more (800 Gt) through respiration, migration and faecal matter (i.e. through the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP); Pinti et al., 2023; Saba et al., 2021). Mesopelagic fish are estimated to contribute 35% (~280 Gt) of this, leading to calls to better consider mid-water ecosystems when evaluating impacts on ocean carbon. This has implications for the BCP, as sediment plumes from deep-sea mining have the potential to affect mesopelagic fish (Drazen et al., 2020).

Dr Haeckel gave an overview of the current state and understanding of deep-sea mining operations and the mineral resources, with a focus on polymetallic nodules. Polymetallic nodules contain nickel, copper, cobalt, manganese, iron, and many other metals and are found on abyssal plains. To be economically viable, polymetallic mining operations would need to collect 2-3 million tonnes of nodules per year, representing a mining area of 200-300 km² per year. However, due to the dispersal and deposition of the sediment plume beyond the mined area, impacts extend beyond the mining site. The potential impacts on biogeochemical processes and benthic ecosystem functioning in deep-sea sediment habitats were described. While there is still uncertainty around some of the processes and impacts involved, benthic processes are expected recover on a millennial time scale due to the removal of the biologically active surface layer during nodule mining operations (Haeckel et al., 2020; König et al., 2001; Haffert et al., 2020; Volz et al., 2020; Vonnahme et al., 2020), the specific nodule habitat is lost permanently (Boetius & Haeckel, 2018). Current understanding of potential emissions arising from deep-sea mining operations, including the transport of materials and on-land processing were also discussed.

2.1 Future trajectories

Dr Fiona Culhane presented some of the emerging industries that may interact with ocean carbon and deep-sea mining. These activities are developing in the context of food security, green-technology mineral requirements, and climate change trajectories. Emerging industries include the potential development of mesopelagic fisheries and industrial Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR).

Interactions between deep-sea mining, ocean carbon, and emerging industries have implications for ecosystem service trade-offs including in relation to food security and fishing livelihoods; green technology mineral requirements; both natural and enhanced carbon capture and storage; as well as nature for nature's sake and biodiversity.

2.2 Discussion: Ocean Carbon and Deep-Sea Mining

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- How does this compare to dredging?

There is a team in OceanICU that are looking into this, including bottom trawling effects.

- The figures used in the presentations do not show the real scale of impacts, the real scale of the plume and the real depth of the ocean where this takes place. [participant shared the figure below from The Metals Company].

This feedback is important and will be taken into account, particularly in communication materials and outputs. *However, in the sketch by NORI the impact by the return waste plume is completely missing and the spatial scale of annual mining operations and resulting sediment plumes is not shown – it only considers the depth scale – hence it is as inappropriate as any other sketch.*

- It is important to understand the mechanism but also the right dimensions, and the interactions. Diagrams should have text to make sure people read them correctly. Perhaps more diagrams needed.

There is a trade-off in being more accurate and making accessible. The understanding is important and we need to be careful about representations and what they actually mean and will consider this when developing outputs from OceanICU

- A lot of modelling has been done on the sediment plumes and outcomes of models might have been precautionary. It is very difficult to put all these things into one graph, such as the size of mining operations and the resources. Some of the risks estimated might not end up as severe as it might be.

We aim to fill the gaps and improve the models but also the feedback we get from people working in this space is important to produce realistic scenarios, especially where we do not have enough data. These discussions will help to inform that work.

- In the study presented by Dr. Haeckel does it require more time to see if there are extended impacts beyond the study areas?

While the study did measure this area *and can create indices and inform models from this*, it did not fully cover the fine sediment area. Further investigation would be required to cover the full area, and to assess whether this has impacts.

- Were there effects on the rate of oxidation of carbon that is released to CO₂ (remineralisation in the sediments)?

We did try to measure oxygen on the plumes but were not successful. Regarding resuspended plumes, there is some C that would be resuspended. It is lower than the natural fluxes.

3. Survey Results

A survey consisting of 17 questions about ocean carbon and 6 questions about the respondents was distributed online in advance of the workshop to invited participants. The survey was designed to gather initial perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon, prime the participants to start thinking about the links between deep-sea mining and ocean carbon, and assess baseline knowledge and gaps to prepare presentations for the workshop itself.

The first question asked what people think of when they hear the term ‘*ocean carbon*’ (Box 3.1). The most common themes emerging from this question were about the role of marine organisms in the carbon cycle and showed that respondents recognise the ocean as a carbon sink and the relevance to climate change.

Box 3.1 Themes of the responses to the question: “*What comes to mind when you hear the term ocean carbon?*” (with the number of unique times a theme was mentioned). 18 responses.

- The role of living ocean species and habitats, the biological carbon pump and including ‘blue carbon habitats’ (8)
- Carbon sequestration and the ocean as a sink for carbon (6)
- The importance or role of the ocean in the carbon cycle (5)
- Climate change, including warming and ocean acidification (4)
- The role of non-living elements in storing and cycling carbon (3)
- Emissions (1)

All respondents thought that the ocean is extremely or very important for helping us to manage or improve climate change (Figure 3.1). Fifty-six percent of respondents thought that the links between carbon and deep-sea mining are very or extremely important for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change, while 22% thought these links are moderately important, and a further 22% thought these links had little or no importance (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.1 Responses to the question: “How important is the ocean for helping us to manage or improve climate change?” (19 responses/100%).

Figure 3.2 Responses to the question: “How important are the links between carbon and deep-sea mining for understanding the Biological Carbon Pump and/or climate change?” (18 responses/95%).

The most common ways respondents thought that ocean carbon affects deep-sea mining (Box 3.2) relate to the impacts of carbon management measures on DSM activity. In terms of the ways DSM can affect ocean carbon (Box 3.3), respondents thought about the disturbance of carbon sequestration processes and stored carbon. There was also uncertainty, in particular about the scale of any impacts.

Box 3.2 Themes of the responses to the question: “*In what ways, if any, do you think ocean carbon affects or influences deep-sea mining?*” 12 responses.

- Operational limitations: Ocean carbon could determine if, where, when, and how deep-sea mining occurs due to ocean carbon reserves and management and regulatory implications (5)
- No impact, or only impacts the other way round (4)
- Uncertain or unknown (3)
- Perception of DSM: Ocean carbon could create publicity or expectations from NGOs in relation to deep sea mining (1)

Box 3.3 Themes of the responses to the question: “*In what ways, if any, do you think deep-sea mining affects ocean carbon?*” 12 responses.

- Disturbance of sequestration processes and carbon cycle and the biodiversity involved in these processes (7)
- Disturbance of stored carbon in sediments (4)
- Magnitude of impact – perspectives range from insignificant, localised to large and irreversible (3)
- DSM will support decarbonisation through lower carbon intensity mining compared to land-based and by providing minerals for renewable technologies (2)
- Unknown/uncertain (2)

Thirty-nine per cent of respondents were concerned or very concerned, and the same proportion (39%) were moderately concerned about the carbon footprint of deep-sea mining (Figure 3.3). Emissions due to operations and transport, and sediment disturbance were the factors most respondents attributed to the carbon footprint of deep-sea mining (Box 3.4).

Figure 3.3 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about the carbon footprint of deep-sea mining?” (18 responses/95%).

Box 3.4 Themes of the responses to the question: “Which aspect of deep-sea mining do you think are most important for its carbon footprint?” 14 responses.

- Fuel emissions including due to at-sea and on-land processing and operations (10)
- Seabed and sediment disturbance and release of stored carbon from seabed (7)
- Transport and shipping (5)
- Impact on the biological carbon pump and natural processes (4)
- Decarbonisation through mineral supply (1)
- Need carbon footprint comparison with on-land mining methods (1)
- Uncertainty (1)

Concern about deep-sea mining releasing carbon from sediments was split, with 50% concerned or very concerned, and 50% only somewhat, a little or not at all concerned (Figure 3.4). Three respondents mentioned that the scale of this issue would not be significant, two respondents mentioned that we need greater understanding around the mechanisms and impacts. One respondent thought that the disturbance of ocean carbon should be taken seriously, irrespective of whether there would be a detectable impact in atmospheric carbon concentrations.

There was greater concern amongst respondents about the impacts of disturbing the water column on the BCP, with 61% concerned or very concerned (Figure 3.5). Four respondents mentioned the scale and/or severity, and whether these would be significant. Three respondents highlighted the need for more evidence on the mechanisms and impacts. Two respondents mentioned that we should be very concerned about the risk. One respondent questioned whether impacts could be alleviated by taking a different approach to discharging waste. Two respondents drew comparisons to other impacts – both natural and from fishing or dredging.

Figure 3.4 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about the fact that disturbing the seabed through dredging/mining activities can cause carbon to be released from sediments?” (18 responses/95%).

Figure 3.5 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about the fact that disturbing the water column through mining activities (e.g. via suspended material and return waste water plume effects) can cause disruption to the Biological Carbon Pump?” (18 responses/95%).

Plankton and microbes were the biological components most frequently mentioned by respondents as being important for capturing and storing carbon (Box 3.5). In addition, macroalgae and macrophyte blue carbon habitats, reef habitats and larger animals were also mentioned. Benthic and deep-sea organisms were considered to be the organisms most at risk by most respondents (Box 3.6). Although the organisms identified as most at risk were not the same as those identified as most important for capturing and storing ocean carbon by most respondents, 61% of respondents were concerned or very concerned that the impacts of deep-sea mining on these organisms would have the potential to affect ocean carbon (Figure 3.6). Two respondents highlighted the need for further investigation.

Box 3.5 Themes of the responses to the question: “Which living organisms do you consider important for capturing and storing ocean carbon?” 13 responses.

- Phytoplankton/plankton (7)
- Microbes, bacteria and fungi (7)
- Seagrasses, macroalgae, mangroves, salt marsh (4)
- Reefs, including oyster reefs, and benthic invertebrates (3)
- Larger animals including mammals and fish (3)
- All living organisms, the whole ecosystem (2)
- Forests (1)

Box 3.6 Themes of the responses to the question: “What organisms/habitats are most at risk from deep-sea mining activities?” 14 responses

- Benthic, deep sea organisms including abyssal plain, seamount, hydrothermal vent, reef and polymetallic nodule communities (9)
- Deep sea ecosystems (in general) (4)
- Pelagic organisms (3)
- The whole ecosystem and the food chain (3)
- It depends on location, types of activity, technology used and how it is managed (3)
- No extinction risk (2)
- Marine mammals and migratory species (2)

Figure 3.6 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you that impacts from deep-sea mining activities affecting these organisms or habitats have the potential to affect ocean carbon?” (18 responses/95%).

Marine geoengineering, including carbon capture and storage, was the most commonly mentioned new or growing marine activity (Box 3.7). Ninety percent of those who responded to this question were at concerned or very concerned about new marine activities (Figure 3.7), with one respondent mentioning the potential impacts on marine biodiversity, despite claims about benefits. Another respondent mentioned that other marine activities are much more extensive than deep-sea mining will ever be, and that they were therefore more concerned about these other activities.

Box 3.7 Themes of the responses to the question: “Are you aware of any new or growing marine activities that are related to carbon and climate change? (Which ones)” (11 responses).

- Carbon capture and storage technologies and marine geoengineering (6)
- Offshore renewable energy (2)
- Hydrogen and nuclear marine power (1)
- Shipping (1)
- Dredging (1)
- Fishing (1)
- Marine mining (1)
- Military (1)

Figure 3.7 Responses to the question: “How concerned are you about these activities?” (10 responses/53%).

Box 3.7 Themes of the responses to the question: “Are you aware of any established or new activities that deep-sea mining may interact with?” (9 responses).

- Fishing (6)
- Communication cables (4)
- None (3)
- Geoengineering (1)
- Carbon offsetting schemes (1)

The most common response to whether there would be implications for respondents’ work was that none were expected or that it would depend on various factors, as this is still a ‘potential’ industry (Box 3.8). Other issues that respondents wanted to address were related to other consequences or mechanisms of impact of deep-sea mining not addressed; longer term implications of deep-sea mining; and socio-economic concerns including links to cultural heritage and communities (Box 3.9).

Box 3.8 Themes of the responses to the question: “Based on your responses to the previous questions, will there be implications for you in your work? (e.g. changes to your practices, policies, focal areas, etc.) (Briefly describe)” (10 responses).

- None (4)
- Proactive research required and establish research funding programmes (2)
- Regulations under development (1)
- Potential changes to environmental management practices (1)
- Depends on research outcomes (1)
- Need for mitigation of impacts of deep sea mining (1)

Box 3.9 Are there any other topics related to deep-sea mining and ocean carbon, not covered in this survey, that are of interest/concern to you? Briefly describe:

- Light pollution and underwater noise (1)
- Could deep sea mining enhance natural ocean carbon burial processes? (1)
- Effect of geopolitical strategies (1)
- Fate of end-of-life mining sites (1)
- If no deep sea mining, what are the implications for land-based carbon? (1)
- Longer term implications of permanent ecosystem damage and the need to get to net-zero (1)
- Common heritage of humankind, future generations and indigenous groups (1)

4. Deep-sea mining – Ocean Carbon Social Ecological System

One of the goals of the workshop was to produce a mental model, together with the stakeholders, of the elements of a deep-sea mining – ocean carbon system and the interactions between those elements. The first step of this was to brainstorm on what elements should be included. This was followed by building the model through discussion of how the elements interact. This type of mental map is a causal model of the system, represented by a network of elements and the relationships between them (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2022). The connections aim to capture the complexity of the system, but notes or annotations can also be used to represent different beliefs. This type of approach is an iterative process, and the model can be built on and further developed over time.

4.1 Elements of a Deep-sea mining System

In the first step, the elements of the deep-sea mining – ocean carbon system were identified. The elements were structured around the categories: sectors, pressures, ecosystem components and ecosystem services or socio-economic factors. Participants of the workshop were asked four questions, in turn:

- What sectors are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the deep sea?
- What pressures are most relevant in relation to ocean carbon in the deep sea?
- What ecosystem elements should be included in the analyses? At what level of detail?
- What ecosystem services and socio-economic factors should be included in the model? i.e. what are the trade-offs you are concerned about?

Participants could suggest their responses through Slido polls (slido.com) for each question. The polls appeared as live Word Clouds that participants could view (Figure 3.8). After a first round of answers, prompts (Appendix 8.5) were shown to participants to identify if there were other categories that they would add or remove from these lists. The final list per category can be seen in Table 3.1.

Figure 4.1 Word clouds of elements of the deep-sea ocean carbon social-ecological system, as chosen by participants of the workshop. See Table 3.1 for full lists of elements.

Table 4.1 Full list of components proposed by participants.

Sector	Frequency
Fishing (including trawling, nets, mesopelagic and deep-sea fisheries)	11
Deep-Sea Mining	8
Oil & Gas (including ultra-deep)	7
Marine geo-engineering and carbon dioxide removal	6
All energy intensive industries	3
Others: Dredging; Waste dumping; Communication cables; Shipping; Wind farms	1 vote each
Pressure	Frequency
Habitat and biodiversity disturbance and loss including loss of ecosystem functions and removal of biomass	12
Climate change, atmospheric CO ₂ and disruption of carbon cycle	11
Sediment disturbance including removal, sedimentation and particle motion	6
Acidification	3
Pollution including light, vibration, sediment plume, noise and plastic	2
Habitat restoration and marine conservation	2
Others: Deoxygenation; CDR schemes; Methane Hydrate Stability; Microbial Activity	1 each
Ecosystem component	Frequency
Ecosystem structure, functions, dynamics and integrity	13
Characteristics of communities: vertical migration patterns; sensitivity to pressures; geographical distribution; representativeness; biomass; life history; community level	9
Indicator sensitive and key species, sequestering species	5
Pelagic species, including zoo- and phyto-plankton, neuston, mesopelagics	5
Microbes, including chemosynthetic bacteria	4
Benthic meio- and macro-fauna	4
Habitat and ecological connectivity	4
Carbon flow and remineralisation	4
Mineral resource including metals and nodules	3
Physical characteristics: depth; ocean currents and mixing	3
Others: Unidentified species; toxicity; complexity; wider Earth interactions; biodiversity; marine mammals	1 each
Ecosystem service/socio-economic factor	Frequency
Climate regulation	9
Cultural heritage	7
Carbon Sequestration and Storage	5
Metal Provision including metal security and demand for minerals	4
Marine genetic and medicinal resources	4
Intrinsic Value of Nature and Biodiversity	4
Nutrient Cycling and Productivity	3
Equity and communities	3
Oxygen	2
Biodiversity	2
Fisheries and food security	2
Jevon's paradox	2
Others: Climate change trade-offs; Ocean chemistry; Employment; Regulatory and governance framework; Lifecycle carbon footprint	1 each

4.2 Components Discussion

Participants questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- “Jevon’s paradox” was mentioned in relation to concerns that arise when people think that deep-sea mining will replace other forms of (*on-land*) mining. The argument that deep-sea mining will replace other more polluting land-based mining, might not be the case. Competition and market drivers might make a counter argument to that case.
This is a valid point. There is some expectation that on-land mining will move to deep-sea mining. The issues surrounding deep-sea mining of polymetallic nodules and related to the cost-effectiveness to mining these materials was highlighted by Dr Haeckel. The efficiency in using these resources and increasing demand is relevant but separate *to identifying and assessing the impacts of DSM*.
- Should we include land-based industries to help integrate on-land activities in the models/assessments? Participants agreed with this.
- We should be very specific. Other industries: agricultural industry, fishing, clothing industry. These can be compared conceptually with deep-sea mining. Telecommunication industry, fishing, shipping etc. might have big impacts as well and would be nice to have them. If you merge all together, then you would not be able to compare them with anything. Most of the impacts come from the on-land industries.
Land-based versus deep-sea mining, might be completely outweighed. At the moment, we are more focused on deep sea habitats. We will keep your suggestions, and we may want to separate these industries.
- Erosion is a better term than abrasion in this context. Erosion is used to refer to natural processes. Abrasion is the more commonly used term in marine environments for impacts caused by human activities.
- People have interpreted things in different ways, and our responses can be different depending on the way you ask the question, for example what would be considered as an ecosystem component? If we saw the element prompts first, we might have given different answers. The way the questions are framed characterises the responses that derived from this workshop. The way things are broken down could influence the outcome.
We absolutely agree, however asking for your perceptions first is intentional, as we want to understand your perceptions, before we bias them with our own. That is the reason they are framed the way they are and why we follow up with discussion to clarify and elaborate on meanings and interpretation.
- There are some ecosystem services included in schemes like CICES that aren't noted here.
The list of ecosystem services presented was not exhaustive, just a starting point, we are happy to consider any services that participants feel are relevant.

During the discussion additional categories were added and removed, with comments for the inclusion of neuston, microbial components, and marine mammals (surface / near surface, deep-diving separately).

4.3 Conceptual Model Building

The elements from the first exercise were used as a starting point to build the conceptual model ensuring the inclusion of the focal elements: ‘deep-sea mining and ‘ocean C cycle’ and ‘global C cycle’. This was produced live during the workshop via the online MentalModeler software (www.mentalmodeler.org; Gray et al. 2013). Discussion with the participants informed where links should be (i.e. what connections exist). Through this process, the elements in the model evolved, and understanding of the linkages was elucidated. This resulting model is illustrated in Figure 4.2, with the key elements listed in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.2 Provisional mental model co-produced with stakeholders during the shelf seas workshop using the software MentalModeler. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element: sectors (orange), pressures (blue), ecosystem components (grey), ecosystem services (yellow), socio-economic elements (pink) and climate (green). Links between the nodes are represented by lines. Lines are either positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Note: full consistency check of this model is in progress, some amendments may result from this process.

Table 4.2 The key elements included in the conceptual model.

Sectors	Pressures	Ecosystem Components	Socio-economic & Ecosystem Services	Climate
Deep-sea mining	Emissions	Benthic habitats	Resource provisioning	Global Carbon Cycle
Fisheries	Climate change	Water column	Clean Energy	Ocean Carbon (BCP)
Nodule collection/extraction	Surface substrate removal	Ecosystem functions	Climate Regulation	
	Siltation (sediment disturbance)		Biodiversity	
	Targeted species extraction			
	Bycatch/incidental loss			
	Siltation deposition			
	Siltation resuspension			

4.4 Model Discussion

The extensive discussions to form the model were documented, and the outcomes are illustrated in the previous section. Additional participant questions and comments are provided below in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- This is a really broad context as OceanICU intend to address "Industrial impacts on carbon cycle" which includes many levels... how is this different from workshops where threats from DSM are addressed?
Here we want to see how the industries interact with the threats, the benefits they provide, socio-economic concerns, and overall the broader picture of those elements (both positive and negative). We want to make the connection to society, and include wider societal and ecosystem concerns, whilst also explicitly linking with the ocean carbon cycle.
- Does this project only focus on nodule collection?
In the first instance yes, but other activities are also potentially in scope. The work today will contribute to the numerical model part, including how this industry can be added to the models. At this stage the work is focused on nodules. We would be interested in any other aspect in the future that can also inform the modelling work.
- There was discussion on the terminology used around nodule extraction/collection or non-living extraction (not targeted). There were multiple opinions on phrasing and terminology and implications and interpretations of them. No consensus on what terminology should be used.
- It was highlighted that most of the current discussions are hypothetical. For example, currently there are no regulations that determine which depths discharge plumes should be released. There was a suggestion that the deeper you release the plumes the more technology you will need with implications for operational viability. The consensus was that all eventualities (or as many as possible) should be considered when developing scenarios for modelling.
- It was also highlighted that the relationship between nodules and clean energy and the potential drivers of mining activity are down to policy choices and not a given. There might be a desire or need from the clean energy sector, but as extraction happens the materials might not be used for that purpose.

5. Conclusions

Active engagement from the invited participants led to a successful outcome for the workshop. Through discussion, survey results and building the conceptual models, some key themes emerged relating to ocean carbon. These include:

- **Importance of the ocean in relation climate change and carbon:** The role of the ocean and its living organisms in sequestering and storing carbon needs to be recognised.
- **Biodiversity and habitats:** the importance of biodiversity and habitats was emphasised by participants. We cannot consider carbon alone, without also considering biodiversity.
- **The dimensions of the deep sea and the scale of deep-sea mining activity and its impacts:** The true scale of the deep ocean and the activities that take place there need to be fairly represented, as most current representations do not show this. The scale of activities and impacts was an important point that was raised several times. There is no consensus on whether the scale of impacts will be large and irreversible or insignificant in relation to the scale of oceans and deep sea habitats.
- **Deep-sea ecosystem services:** The role of the deep-sea in supplying multiple ecosystem services, including climate regulation, cultural heritage, genetic and medicinal services, and intrinsic value, in addition to role of deep-sea mining in providing metal security and the meeting demand for minerals need to be considered and balanced.
- **The relationship between on-land and at-sea activities:** this theme was multi-faceted, including discussions around the relative impacts of deep-sea mining on ocean ecosystems and the climate compared to other land based activities or land-based mining. It was highlighted that deep-sea mining may not result in less on-land mining, and that demand for these minerals may increase as technology progresses.
- **Uncertainties in the direction of policy:** the uncertainty of whether this industry will progress at all, or in what form it will progress, and how it would be regulated was an underlying theme across all discussions and inputs by participants. Therefore, modelling work and scenarios should take this into account.
- **Key knowledge and evidence gaps:** were also highlighted as a key issue. These related to the need for further evidence on the mechanisms and scales of impacts, and a lack of evidence on deep-sea habitats themselves. Any assumptions in the modelling work and scenarios need to be clearly documented and communicated.

The above points and themes will guide the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU. They will help form the basis of scenarios to test using a range of modelling approaches, including Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN), and help inform the basis of an integrative risk assessment centred around carbon.

5.1 Action Items

- Summary report to be written and circulated for review and feedback.
- The model (Figure 4.2) will be consistency-checked for anomalies and issues, and ground-truthed against available evidence and in consultation with stakeholders in a future session.
- Follow-up meetings will be arranged with this stakeholder group as well as with shelf seas and high-sea fishing stakeholders.
- It was discussed that we should separate the effects of deep-sea mining into depth categories. We may refer back to the stakeholder group for feedback on this.
- Participants requested a set of definitions for the pressures used (see Appendix 8.5).

7. References

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8. Appendices

8.1 Agenda

Time (GMT)	Program
09.00 – 09.30	Introduction to workshop, housekeeping, and OceanICU project
09.30 – 09.40	Results from the pre-workshop survey
09.40 – 10.40	Presentation (30 minutes) and open discussion (30 minutes) on deep-sea mining and carbon
10.40 - 11.00	Exercise: elements of an ocean carbon-deep-sea mining system
11.00 – 11.20	Break
11.20 – 12.40	Exercise: co-producing a model of an ocean carbon-deep-sea mining system
12.40 – 13.00	Wrap up and final words

8.2 Acronyms

- BCP: Biological Carbon Pump
- CDR: Carbon Dioxide Removal
- CO₂: Carbon dioxide
- DSM: Deep-Sea Mining
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- EBFM: Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management
- EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management
- ES: Ecosystem Services
- Gt: Gigatonne, 1 Gt = 1000 million tonnes
- HVO: Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
- ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- NET: Negative Emissions Technologies
- OceanICU: Integrated Carbon Understanding – the project behind this workshop:
<https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- SST: Sea Surface Temperature
- VME: Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems

8.3 Participant List

List of participant organisations that attended the workshop (participant names are not provided). Those in grey indicate the meeting organisers and presenters.

	Name	Institution
1	Fiona Culhane	Marine Institute
2	Debbi Pedreschi	Marine Institute
3	Paula Silvar	Marine Institute
4	Robert Runya	Marine Institute
5	Matthias Haeckel	Geomar
6	Richard Sanders	NORCE
7	Mikaela Gomes	World Maritime University
8	Natalya Gallo	NORCE
9		Independent consultant
10		BGR - Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources
11		International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
12		Greenpeace Research Laboratories (Greenpeace International)/University of Exeter
13		University of California, Santa Barbara
14		GSR (Global Sea Mineral Resources)
15		Jan De Nul nv
16		The Pew Charitable Trusts
17		BGR - Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources
18		German Environment Agency
19		Allseas
20		DeepOcean Group
21		Blue Globe Solutions
22		Seas at Risk
23		Project Management Juelich
24		Allseas

8.4 Resources

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- OceanICU webinars (including Mining and Carbon webinar): <https://ocean-icu.eu/webinars/>
- OceanICU: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- Stakeholder Mailing List Sign Up for OceanICU: <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUjoin>
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8.5 Socio-ecological System Components

Sectors

Agriculture
Fishing
Land-based Industry
Military
Nuclear
Research
Shipping
Telecommunications
Tourism/Recreation
Waste Water
Dredging
Ocean NETS/CDR
Aquaculture

Ecosystem Components

Cephalopods
Demersal Elasmobranchs
Demersal Fish
Pelagic Elasmobranchs
Pelagic Fish
Reptiles
Seabirds
Marine Mammals
Epipelagic
Littoral Soft Sediment
Littoral Rock and Reef
Shallow Soft Sediment
Shallow Rock and Reef
Shelf Soft Sediment
Shelf Rock and Reef

Ecosystem Services

Seafood - wild
Seafood - Aquaculture
Raw materials (Biotic/Abiotic)
Genetic Materials
Nursery populations and habitats
Refuge habitats
Global climate regulation
Feeding grounds
Chemical composition of oceans and atmosphere
Cultural services

Socio-Economic Factors

Wages
Fish prices
Fuel prices
Gentrification
Fleet diversification
Safety at Sea
Equity
Quota
Management
Governance
Enforcement
Fishing Behaviour
Community Impacts
Processing/Processors
Livelihoods
Policy

Pressures

This list of pressures and their definitions is adapted from those listed in the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive³ and White et al., (2013)⁴

Pressure	Definition
Abrasion	Physical interaction of human activities with the seafloor and with seabed fauna/flora causing physical damage and/or mortality (e.g. from trawling or anchoring).
Bycatch/ Incidental Loss	Extraction (and subsequent mortality) of any incidental non-target marine fauna (vertebrate or invertebrate) from their natural habitat (e.g. by commercial fishing, recreational angling and collecting/harvesting).
Contaminating Compounds	Introduction of manmade and non-manmade compounds such as pesticides, antifoulants, pharmaceuticals, heavy metals and hydrocarbons into marine waters
Electromagnetic Fields	Change in the amount and/or distribution and/or periodicity of electromagnetic energy emitted in a marine area (e.g. from electrical sources such as underwater cables)
Invasive Species	Introduction of non-indigenous species and translocations by the activities of a particular sector (e.g. through exchange of ballast waters by shipping or from release of individuals from aquaculture)
Litter	Litter originating from numerous sources but entering the marine environment and consisting of different materials including: plastics, metal, glass, rubber, wood and cloth
Noise	Underwater noise created from shipping, acoustic surveys, etc
Extraction of Non-living Resources	Includes sand and gravel (aggregates) extraction, removal of surface substrates for exploration of seabed and subsoil, or removal of seawater for e.g. cooling industrial plants or for desalination
Organic Matter	Organic enrichment and any subsequent deoxygenation, e.g. from industrial and sewage effluent into rivers and coastal areas, or from the waste from aquaculture or from fishing discards
Radionuclides	Introduction of radionuclides into marine waters
Sealing	Physical loss of habitat from sealing by permanent construction (e.g. Coastal defences, wind turbines)
Siltation/Smothering	Cover habitat surface with materials falling to the seafloor from activities in the water column (e.g. waste substances from aquaculture cages), on land (e.g. in runoff or effluent), or around activities (e.g. around trawling gear), or from disposal of materials onto the seafloor (e.g. disposal of materials from dredging). Smothering may lead to reduced functioning (e.g. feeding) or mortality of benthic animals living on, or in, the seafloor.
Species Extraction	Extraction (and subsequent mortality) of any target marine fauna (vertebrate or invertebrate) from their natural habitat (e.g. by commercial fishing, recreational angling and collecting/harvesting)
Thermal changes	Change in temperature of the water (average, range or variability) e.g. due to outfalls from industrial plants

³ EC. 2008. Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive). Official Journal of the European Union. L164: 19-40.

⁴ White, L., Koss, R.S., Knights, A.M., Eriksson, A. and Robinson, L.A. 2013. ODEMM Linkage Framework Userguide (Version 2). ODEMM Guidance Document Series No.3. EC FP7 project (244273) 'Options for Delivering Ecosystem-based Marine Management'. University of Liverpool. ISBN: 978-0-906370-87-6: 14 pp.

GHG emissions (to air)	Emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere
pH changes	Changes in pH (average, range or variability) e.g. due to run off from land-based industry
Salinity changes	Change in salinity (average, range or variability), e.g. due to outfalls from industrial plants or alterations in coastal structures affecting mixing
Death/injury by collision	Death or injury of marine fauna due to impact with moving parts of a human activity, e.g. marine mammals with ships/jet skis, seabirds with wind turbines etc
Precipitation changes	Large scale climatic change